

THE ESSENCE OF THE RELIGIOUS POLICY PURSUED BY THE
SOVIET GOVERNMENT IN THE UZBEK SSR

Rustamov Zokir Toirovich

Independent Researcher of the Uzbekistan

National Pedagogical University

E-mail: zokirtoirovich040@gmail.com

Abstract. This article examines the nature and essence of the anti-religious policy implemented by the Soviet government against Islam, the measures carried out within this policy, and the changes that occurred as a result. The study reveals how historical monuments, mosques, madrasahs, religious institutions, and pilgrimage sites were destroyed or left in ruins during this period.

Keywords: Turkestan, Islam, clergy, Soviet government, Muslims, mosque, madrasah, mausoleum.

Researchers note that relations between the Soviet government and Islam generally passed through three stages. During the first stage (1917–1927), the central Soviet government sought compromise with Muslim clergy and attempted to use them to export the revolution to Eastern countries. During the second stage (beginning in 1927), the Soviet authorities launched a harsh struggle against Islam. Religious leaders were subjected to severe persecution, most mosques were destroyed, and a large number of clergy members became victims of repression. The third stage (1944–1989) was characterized by a policy in which Muslim clergy were forced to pay heavy taxes and make so-called voluntary contributions to the Peace Fund. After a short post-war period, the construction of new mosques and the opening of Islamic educational institutions were permitted. However, during Khrushchev's anti-religious campaign, some previously reopened mosques were closed again, and pilgrimages to sacred Muslim sites were prohibited.

On the eve of the establishment of the Uzbek SSR, the Central Committee of the Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks) and the government of the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic abandoned their relatively “soft” policy toward religious institutions and organizations that had been pursued between 1920 and 1922. At the Twelfth Congress of the Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks) in April 1923, a special resolution was adopted calling for intensified anti-religious propaganda. The resolution emphasized that millions of citizens of the republic had to be completely liberated from religious superstitions [1].

The Soviet government also exploited the existing differences between “conservative” and “progressive” Muslim clergy. Progressive clerics advocated reforming Muslim schools, delivering sermons in native languages, improving the status of women, and changing the practice of zakat distribution. By supporting these “progressive” clerics in their struggle against the “conservative” clergy, the Soviet authorities sought ultimately to weaken the influence of both groups among the Muslim population.

During the first years of Soviet rule, Islamic holidays in Muslim regions were officially recognized as public holidays. Eid al-Adha and Eid al-Fitr were celebrated as national holidays [2].

Beginning in 1927, however, the Soviet government launched a wave of repression against Muslim clergy. The struggle against Islam took many forms, including the closure and destruction of mosques, the deprivation of voting rights for religious leaders, the confiscation of waqf properties and zakat funds, and extensive anti-religious propaganda campaigns. At this stage, the Bolsheviks also began eliminating the so-called progressive Muslim clergy, despite the fact that Soviet power had been established in several Muslim regions with their support.

Between 1929 and 1940, many historical monuments, religious institutions, and organizations were neglected. Mosques, madrasahs, mausoleums, shrines of saints, cemeteries, khanqahs, and other sacred sites fell into ruin. Some mosque

and madrasah buildings were converted into stables, while others were transformed into wine, vodka, or beer production facilities, thereby being deliberately desecrated.

In addition, atheist propaganda was actively promoted throughout the republic through newspapers, radio broadcasts, theaters, clubs, museums, exhibitions, lectures, discussions, and question-and-answer evenings. Competitions such as “Best Anti-Religious Poem,” “Best Anti-Religious Essay,” and “Best Anti-Religious Caricature” were also organized [3]. For example, between 1939 and 1940, thirty different anti-religious publications in the Uzbek language were issued with a total circulation of 470,000 copies. During the same period, approximately 170 articles published in republican newspapers were devoted to criticizing religion.

Following Joseph Stalin’s speech of March 3, 1928, in which he declared that the struggle against kulaks was also a decisive stage in the struggle against religion, believers and religious figures increasingly became targets of repression [4].

In 1929–1930, a large-scale campaign to close mosques was conducted throughout the Soviet Union as part of collectivization policies. Local activists often falsified the signatures of believers and violated legal procedures regulating the closure of religious buildings.

Collectivization, accompanied by the closure of mosques and persecution of Muslim clergy, triggered a number of uprisings in Muslim-populated areas. Military forces were deployed to suppress these revolts, including those that occurred in Central Asia and Kazakhstan.

On October 1, 1929, contrary to the wishes of Muslims and Jews, Sunday was established as the sole official day of rest, while religious holidays were prohibited [5].

During the Great Terror, atheist propaganda was further intensified, particularly in Muslim regions. In the late 1930s, another instrument of atheization was introduced through military service reforms. In 1938–1939, the principle of extraterritorial military service was implemented in the Red Army. Conscripts were required to serve outside their home regions. As a result, recruits from Muslim regions were often sent to areas with little or no Muslim population, while non-Muslim soldiers were stationed in Muslim territories. In 1938, for example, 17,825 individuals were drafted from Central Asia, but only 1,800 remained to serve within the Central Asian Military District [6].

The destruction of mosques and the elimination of clergy were accompanied by ideological campaigns against Islam. One of the most significant developments of the 1930s was the replacement of the traditional Arabic script used by Muslim peoples with the Latin alphabet and later with the Cyrillic alphabet.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the religious policy implemented by the Soviet government in Uzbekistan during the 1920s and 1930s led to the exclusion of Islam from political and cultural life. As a result of anti-religious campaigns, thousands of believers and religious leaders became victims of repression. Nevertheless, despite these efforts, Islam retained an important place in the everyday life, traditions, and social practices of the population.

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